

Contents

Editorial: Harari and the Contemporary World-----	3
Paul Thelakat -----	5
God Stuck in Enlightenment Prejudices	
Henry Jose -----	16
Ignorance is Not Bliss: Reflections on Harari’s Humanistic Challenge to Acknowledge Ignorance	
Carmel Raj D. -----	33
Immigration: Both a Blessing and a Challenge	
Khumtang Y Tikhir -----	51
Meditate: Just Observe and Be	

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Editorial

Harari and the Contemporary World

Yuval Noah Harari (1976-) is an Israeli public intellectual, historian and a professor, Department of History at the Hebrew University, Jerusalem. He has authored three highly acclaimed bestsellers regarding the nature and future of human beings: *Sapiens: A Brief History of Humankind*, *Homo Deus: A Brief History of Tomorrow*, and *21 Lessons for the 21st Century*.

Sapiens tells us how the cognitive revolution, the agricultural revolution and the scientific revolution have affected humans and their fellow organisms.

It's one of those books that can't help but make you feel smarter for having read it. Barack Obama and Bill Gates have undergone that experience, as many prominent persons at Davos and Silicon Valley. The tragic irony is that one of the book's warnings is that we are in danger of becoming an elite-dominated global society. *Homo Deus* (from Latin "Homo"

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meaning man or human and “*Deus*” meaning God) deals more with the abilities acquired by humans (*Homo sapiens*) throughout their existence, and their evolution as the dominant species in the world. The book describes mankind’s current abilities and achievements and attempts to paint an image of the future. Many philosophical issues are discussed, such as humanism, individualism, transhumanism, and mortality. examine possibilities of the future of *Homo sapiens*. The book presupposes that during the 21st century, humanity is likely to make a significant attempt to gain happiness, immortality, and God-like powers and possibilities!

In *21 Lessons for the 21st Century*, Harari explores what it means to be human in an age of bewilderment. This crucial book raises some fundamental questions to ourselves: How can we protect ourselves from nuclear war, ecological cataclysms and technological disruptions? What can we do about the epidemic of fake news or the threat of terrorism?

This issue of the journal takes up four important issues (God, ignorance, immigration and meditation) from this book and explores them further. We look at the relevance of Harari’s vision for the contemporary world with critical eyes.

May this vision make our world more egalitarian and equitable! May we learn from history to use wisely the incredible power available to us through technology!

The Editor